

The Dynamics of Gender Roles: A Reading of Kunzang Choden's *The Circle of Karma*

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Abstract

This paper critically examines the concept of gender as a social construct, highlighting its interplay with societal norms, power hierarchies, and cultural traditions. It focuses on Kunzang Choden's *The Circle of Karma* (2005), which portrays the patriarchal oppression of women in Bhutanese society through the life of Tsomo, the protagonist. The study explores how Tsomo's gender shapes her experiences of marginalization, as societal expectations and familial authority stifle her aspirations for education. Tsomo's journey reflects the systemic subjugation of women, perpetuated by cultural and religious ideologies that link her struggles to "bad karma." As she navigates various challenges, her encounters with other oppressed women deepen her understanding of gender-based inequalities. Ultimately, her decision to embrace monastic life symbolizes both resistance and liberation. This paper argues that Choden's novel critiques patriarchal structures while emphasizing women's resilience in reclaiming identity and agency within oppressive social systems.

Key Words: Gender roles, Women, Patriarchal society, Oppression etc.

Introduction

Gender impacts every aspect of human existence. It is an essential social construct that shapes identities, roles, and social relationships. Gender and Sex are often used interchangeably and synonymously. However, while sex is biological, gender is a socially constructed concept. The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines sex as "the different biological and physiological characteristics of males and females, such as reproductive organs, chromosomes, hormones, etc." and gender as "the socially constructed characteristics of women and men – such as norms, roles and relationships of and between groups of women and men. It varies from society to society and can be changed" ("Sex and Gender"). Gender refers to the characteristics, roles, and behaviours a society considers appropriate for men, women, and other gender identities. American Psychologist Robert Stoller, in his book *Sex and Gender: The Development of Masculinity and Femininity* (1968), first used the term to differentiate between sex and gender to bring out an individual's femininities and masculinity traits. K. Millett, referencing Stoller, suggests that gender identity constitutes any individual's foremost and enduring identity, with profound and lasting implications (Millett 30). She further asserts, drawing from Stoller's insights, that the cultural aspect of gender imparts its psychological character rather than being rooted in biology. Feminists understand that gender encompasses biological aspects (sex) and socially constructed roles and expectations. Judith Butler posits that gender identity emerges through a

series of repeated actions, which individuals of both sexes eventually come to describe within limited yet culturally defined parameters. “The concept of gender identity is a social construction that is politically charged, influenced by other social laws like hetero normatively and the socio-historical framework of patriarchy” (Butler 24). Butler contends that rather than being only influenced by biological variables, our conception of gender identity is formed within certain social, political, and historical settings.

As society develops and changes, conversations about gender have become more prevalent, bringing up topics like violence, representation, and gender equality. However, it is still crucial to have a thorough grasp of the complex interactions between gender construction, power relations, institutional standards, and cultural influences. Gender dynamics, as a fundamental aspect of social structure, play a profound role in shaping individuals' lives and societal norms. The term “dynamics” has a broad and context-dependent meaning. Dynamics refers to the physical or moral driving forces in any domain: social, political, economic, domestic, etc. In this sense, dynamics refers to the forces, factors, or mechanisms that influence and shape the behaviour or development of a system or domain.

The introduction of gender as an analytical category was a significant development in understanding the distinction between biological sex differences and the societal construction of behaviours and traits associated with masculinity or femininity. While biological sex refers to the physiological and anatomical distinctions between males and females, gender encompasses the roles, behaviours, and expectations that societies attribute to individuals based on their perceived sex. The debates on the actual physical or mental impacts of biological differences are exaggerated to support a patriarchal power structure; the affirmation of distinct sexes or genders aims to instil the belief among women that they are inherently better suited for domestic roles; this practice is old as history. Across diverse locations and historical epochs, differing notions about gender exist. The concept of gender, as individuals hold, encompasses a common foundational understanding that involves interactions with how various cultures operate within and beyond gendered realities. The intricate nature of gender encompasses a range of aspects, such as individual rights, identity, and equality. This complexity often intersects with perspectives shaped by caste, creed, community, and religion. The interplay between gender and these additional dimensions contributes to a multifaceted understanding of societal dynamics. Despite the varied interpretations of the term “gender,” it consistently maintains a fundamental link to the social structures that influence power dynamics between the sexes. As a result, each culture and its specific configuration of components within that culture build upon this foundational concept. However, under distinct political and cultural conditions, it adapts and reconfigures notions of gender, gender relations, or gender disparities in diverse ways. The existence of well-defined gender roles, crucial for human interaction, adds complexity to social dynamics. These roles may serve as a way for individuals to convey their gender identity. However, they can also be employed as a mechanism for societal control, and deviating from these roles may result in harmful consequences for the individual.

Defining and establishing clear boundaries for gender roles proves to be exceptionally difficult. Nevertheless, a comprehensive understanding of the term 'gender roles' and its various aspects is essential when examining or observing gender dynamics.

Women have historically been denied the ability to vote, which is a form of discrimination based on gender and the widespread cultural belief that women should be subservient. This phenomenon was deeply rooted in traditional gender roles and patriarchal structures that positioned women as inferior to men. Gender roles have been the primary players that have curtailed the freedom of women. Gender roles are essential to the proper operation of the social machine, but this assertion has been debated over time, irrespective of their impact. Proponents argue that the established gender roles provide a societal structure and help maintain order, while critics say that rigid gender roles can perpetuate inequality and limit individual freedom. Culture is the primary determinant of gender roles, with many societies assigning caregiving responsibilities to males and designating women as homemakers. While progress has been made, gender-based discrimination and societal expectations continue to be issues in various parts of the world. Beyond fieldwork and housework, women are increasingly becoming the primary breadwinners in their families in Bhutanese society. Women have also been entering politics and government in recent years. In 2013, Lyonpo Dorji Choden was appointed as the first female minister. Women work in various professions, including dentistry, medicine, engineering, aviation, law enforcement, and an increasing number of administrative support roles. Tashi Dema, in her article *Women in Bhutan: the Gender Discussion* (2020), compiled a list of statistics that shows the gap in employment between men and women in Bhutan. She mentioned that during a "meet the press" session, Prime Minister Tshering Tobgay stated that women comprised 35.5% of the 26,954 civil servants in 2016. In the last ten years, that represents a 77% increase. However, the unemployment rate for women is high (4.5 per cent) compared to the jobless rate for men (1.8 per cent), and the possibilities for professional progression are poor for those employed. Additionally, only 10% of the civil service—25 women to 228 men—held executive and expert positions, even though women comprise 35.3% of the workforce. According to the 2015 labour force survey data, there were roughly 159,919 female labour contributors and 184,574 male labour contributors. Given that the labour force participation rate is 55.9 for women and 71.2 for men, the poll also discovered a gender gap in terms of overall employment. According to the survey, women typically have lower-quality employment than males since they are employed in low-paying industries like forestry and agriculture, which employ 30.5% of all women. Women have historically faced intrinsic discrimination in the fields of politics, education, work, health, and the rule of law due to cultural beliefs and behaviours. The Prime Minister faced controversy when he uploaded a picture of a female *Gup* (elected village leader) offering the wine oblation on Facebook, known locally as the "*Marchang*," as this was usually the responsibility of male authorities. In some rural places, there is still a superstition that men are superior to women by nine noble human births. As a result, men are referred to as *Kep phoja* (superior male), while

women are disparagingly called *Aumsu mo rem* (helpless women). Another problem is that women are not permitted to visit a *Goenkhang*, a temple or monastery's inner sanctuary (Dema, 2020). While some Bhutanese women have questioned the rationality of such behaviours, many seem to have accepted it. In isolated regions of the nation, the custom of night hunting—where boys visit a girl's home at night to court her—is still practised. Although these methods are said to aid men in finding mates, they have also resulted in some rural women being used by public workers and other individuals who travel to rural communities for both personal and professional purposes. With children born outside of marriage, the practice has left many women to fend for themselves. Society establishes moral and social conduct norms that apply to men and women. Even individuals with limited intellectual capabilities can discern the inherent imbalance within these codes. Significant discrimination exists in the rights and obligations assigned to men and women. Women are often expected to be subservient, while men are anticipated to assume dominant roles in society. Despite women playing the roles of mothers, wives, sisters, and daughters, their status in terms of sexual relationships with men has historically been subordinate to that of men.

Kunzang Choden, through her novel *The Circle of Karma* (2005), depicts the Bhutanese society of the 1950s and 1960s as patriarchal. She focuses mainly on the relationships that evolve between men and women within Bhutan's historically patriarchal society. She contends that societal structure like marriage is exploited to maintain the subjugation of women. Under the guise of this institution, women are victimised. In the novel, the men and women are depicted as conforming to typical thought patterns, gender roles, and gender identities. Consequently, the gender dynamics within the cohabitation arrangements mirror those found in traditional marriages, with men assuming dominant roles and women subverting to their authority. This portrayal underscores the persistence of conventional gender norms and power structures within the relationships depicted in the narrative. Marriage, intended to regulate relationships between men and women for the benefit of both parties, has failed to protect women. Instead, the social institution has been co-opted by a male-dominated culture and wielded as a weapon against women. Men often exploit it to control women. An example of a narrative that singles out unmarried women is illustrated in the story of Nazom in the novel. This narrative exposes the hypocrisy inherent in the proclaimed sanctity of marriage and marital relationships. Society tends to turn a blind eye to the extramarital affairs of married men, yet there is unanimous condemnation for a woman involved in adulterous relationships. Pema slashes Nazom's nose for having an affair with her husband, yet the husband, who shares responsibility, is noticeably absent. In matters concerning relationships between a man and a woman outside the confines of marriage, as seen in the case of Nazom and Pema's husband, society has consistently been biased in blaming the woman. Without any protection, a woman like Nazom becomes vulnerable to the moralistic judgments that people typically believe they should uphold as part of social obligations. Similarly, the main protagonist, Tsomo, attempts to harm the woman who has taken her husband. However, Gaylong Sherab intervenes, preventing her from

committing this act and helping her regain her composure. He questions Tsomo, “Women have to learn to think things through. Why do women always blame each other when their husbands are unfaithful?” (Choden 2005, 269). Even in situations where both genders share equal responsibility for their participation in an affair, society tends to criticise women exclusively. Choden criticises the dynamics of woman-to-woman relationships in society within the story. She highlights that women often perceive each other as competitors, irrespective of their closeness or influence. This portrayal suggests a pervasive perception where, regardless of the bond between women, there is an inherent tendency to see one another as adversaries. Dechen Choki experiences repeated sexual assault by Lajab, and disappointingly, no one, not even her friend Tsomo, comes to her rescue. Instead, she endures taunts and teasing from fellow labourers who view her as Lajab’s favourite. The situation takes a more harrowing turn when Lajab’s wife confronts Dechen Choki, accusing her of being a “husband-stealer and a whore” (Choden 122). In a violent act, she attacks Dechen, rubbing chili powder into her eyes. Dechen stands helplessly, overwhelmed with shame, unable to confront the situation. Even Tsomo, Dechen Choki’s friend, refrains from revealing the truth and utters, “Enough now. Why don’t you look after your husband better? This would not have happened if you had looked after him better.” (Choden 123). These are the exact words Tsomo’s sister Kesang had used when Tsomo confronted her about Wangchen. In society, there is a tendency for both men and women to criticize and stigmatize a woman for perceived promiscuity swiftly. Meanwhile, charging a man with the same offense is often met with less ease and scrutiny. Engaging in infidelity with both a mistress and a wife within the confines of marriage appears to be normalized behavior for men. In both scenarios, women end up as the victims.

Tsomo adheres to the expected gender roles for women, embracing the role of a submissive wife and daughter while upholding patriarchal standards. However, rather than protecting her, this conformity makes her susceptible to male abuse and marginalizes her within society. In this process, she is either wholly disregarded or systematically dismantled. Kunzang Choden brings out the reality of the lack of freedom for a woman in choosing to live a life. Since her early years, Tsomo has been educated about the perceived lower status of her gender. She asks her mom, “Where is the furthest I can travel to Mother?” Her mother tells her: “Where? I don’t know. Where can a girl travel to?” “Where can girls travel?” (Choden 2). Tsomo yearns to be reborn as a man in her next life, recognizing that being born male comes with inherent advantages, including a more favorable birth status and the opportunity for education. Throughout the novel, Tsomo repeatedly laments and echoes the phrase “I am only a woman” (Choden 23). Older women validate this perspective by concurring, affirming that they, as women, should be less ambitious and more subdued, emphasizing the inherent differences between men and women.

In this story, women undergo social conditioning and training that reinforces rituals and practices to solidify their status as secondary and subservient. From a young age, girls are taught to embody qualities stereotypically associated with women, including selflessness, nurturing, and motherhood. “Female family roles are traditionally understood to include relationship maintenance and an overall effort at keeping kin close and connected. Women play expressive roles, taking care of the home and emotional life of a family” (Flynn 65). Tsomo’s mother emphasizes the importance of learning submission, working in the fields, managing household chores, and discouraging questioning, all underlining the societal expectations imposed on women. Tsomo’s mother instills in her the belief that a woman’s purpose is to bring happiness to others by attending to their needs. The emphasis is placed on seeking self-fulfillment through marital responsibilities and embracing the role of a mother. This perspective reflects traditional societal expectations for women, emphasizing their roles in marriage and motherhood as the primary sources of fulfillment and purpose in life. This narrative highlights the ingrained gender roles and the pressure on women to conform to traditional ideals, reinforcing their subordinate position in society. As Simone De Beauvoir says, “One is not born, but rather becomes, woman” (qtd. in Butler 35). At times, Tsomo questions her role as a mother and the prospect of bearing children, reflecting on her mother’s selfless dedication to the family’s needs. Tsomo observed her mother remaining silent and refraining from expressing grievances while her father neglected his responsibilities and immersed himself in religious activities. Despite the challenges she endured, Tsomo’s mother consistently maintained a respectful and loyal demeanor toward her husband. Tsomo often witnessed her mother tirelessly catering to the preferences of others without prioritizing her well-being. The enduring image of her mother, seated by the hearth, simultaneously stirring a pot on the stove with her right hand and feeding a baby in her lap, breathless and with a swollen pregnant belly, remains etched in Tsomo’s mind even today. “The woman is not encouraged to take her needs seriously, to explore them, to try to act on them as a separate individual... instead the woman is encouraged to concentrate on the needs and development of man” (Miller 18). Tsomo’s father, inconsiderate of his wife’s health, consistently makes her bear more children, driven by the belief that a large family is a great blessing. However, he overlooked his wife’s well-being concerns and the family’s wealth. Tragically, Tsomo’s mother succumbed while attempting to deliver another child, a situation exacerbated by disregard for her health and the family’s welfare. Following her mother’s death, Tsomo, as the eldest daughter, is thrust into the responsibility of taking on maternal roles for her siblings. Within a year of her mother’s passing, Tsomo’s father introduces another wife. Women like Tsomo often attributed their misfortunes to karmic repercussions. As the eldest daughter in her family, Tsomo bore the weight of responsibilities, leaving little room for personal decision-making. Traditionally, male children in a family have often been perceived as having a greater need for education than females. This perspective stems from the belief that well-educated males earning good wages will financially support their parents. This attitude reflects traditional gender roles and expectations, where the economic contribution of sons is prioritized over that of daughters. Despite Tsomo’s desire for education, her father dismissed the idea,

insisting that women should focus on household chores. He says, “You are a girl. You are different. You learn other things that will make you a good woman and a good wife. Learn to cook, weave, and all those things. A woman does not need to know how to read and write” (Choden 21). She seeks reassurance from her mother, but her hopes diminish when she notices a smile of resignation and acceptance on her mother’s face. In Tsomo’s household, while boys receive education, Tsomo is trained by her mother to learn essential household tasks such as cooking, washing, weaving, and cleaning. This gendered division of labor is emphasized as crucial for girls, with the expectation that these skills will contribute to their ability to manage a household, a quality deemed important for their future marriages. This reflects traditional gender roles where girls are often prepared for domestic responsibilities while boys are prioritized for formal education. A prevalent stereotype perpetuated in patriarchal families reinforces gender differences, depicting the man as the breadwinner and the woman as the primary caregiver for the home and children. This ideology often leads to girls receiving education primarily focused on domestic responsibilities, cultural norms, and traditions, as these attributes are perceived as essential for fulfilling their future roles as wives and mothers. The discouragement of girls from pursuing higher education and economic empowerment is rooted in the reinforcement of marriage as their destined path, completing their societal role and existence. Kunzang illustrates that in Bhutanese society, when a woman is pregnant, there is a customary purification ceremony known as Tsangma, which she is expected to undergo. Pregnancy is viewed as unclean until purified, as there is a belief that unpurified pregnancies may disturb the gods. Consequently, if natural calamities befall the village, women are often blamed for these occurrences. In the novel, Tsomo’s friend Chimme experiences an out-of-wedlock pregnancy, and the father of her unborn child reneges on his promises to marry her. When the crowd gathers to witness the pregnancy purification ceremony, Chimme faces humiliation and shame. However, she remains resilient, holding her head high. Tsomo, witnessing her friend’s ordeal, attributes such trials to karma. Chimme raises poignant questions about women’s position in society, expressing frustration over the disparity between men and women. She questions why men, despite their actions, often escape consequences while women bear the brunt of the repercussions and become the primary victims, enduring the suffering that ensues. She says, “Men are really lucky. They can do something and then deny all responsibility. But for us women, there is no way we can get away. We are accountable for everything we do” (Choden 43). Ultimately, Chimme, despite questioning the societal injustice and gender disparity, resigns herself to her fate and attributes her position to her karma. She speculates, “This is my karma. Whatever happens, does so only because it has to happen. But I did not have enough merits to have the father of my baby for the public show tonight. I hope you have better karma than mine.” (Choden 43) Chimme goes so far as to express that she would consider herself doubly culpable if her actions unknowingly caused a monk to break his vows of celibacy.

Tsomo marries Wangchen and commits to be a devoted wife and a caring sister. She internalizes her mother's teachings about being a virtuous woman and wife, striving to embody those principles in her life. Tsomo experiences the heartbreak of a miscarriage and, despite her grief, faces rebuke from her husband, Wangchen. Instead of consoling her, he attributes her suffering to karma and insists she must move forward. Later, Wangchen betrays Tsomo by engaging in a relationship with her sister, Kesang. The societal norms emphasize gentility, obedience, and submissiveness as virtues for women. When a woman lacks these qualities, she is promptly and disapprovingly labeled a misfit. This harsh judgment is evident in the case of Tsomo, who dares to oppose her husband's illicit relationship with her sister Kesang. Tsomo, on the other hand, gets to know about her husband's previous marriage only after their marriage. This leads Tsomo to internalize the Karma that just as she had taken away someone else's husband, her husband is taken away from her. She believes that her fate is justified. Wangchen, failing to take responsibility for his actions, resorts to drinking and subjects Tsomo to abuse instead of addressing the issues in their relationship. Tsomo silently endures the hardships for an extended period, rationalizing that he is a man and she is a woman. In these moments, she grasped the sentiment behind the many women who expressed, "Being born a woman is to suffer." (Choden 92). Recognizing that she had no place in Wangchen's life, Tsomo decided to leave her home one day. Along her journey, she encounters women like Dechen Choki, who, too, have become victims of gender-related challenges and societal expectations. Choki shares how she was abused and sexually molested by her stepfather and how neither her mother nor she could do anything as they were dependent on him. As they share each other's tragic experiences, Choki remarks: "Our stories are so similar and yet so different. Everything happened because we are women. You loved a man and suffered. I hated the man and suffered" (Choden 109). In the novel, Tsomo continually faces reminders that living alone is not an option for her. However, she discovers a sense of independence and freedom upon reaching Kalimpong. As Dechen Choki marries and Tsomo finds herself alone, she embarks on a pilgrimage to Dorjitan. During her stay there, Ap Thinley brings a proposal from Lhatu, but she rejects it. Unexpectedly, Lhatu arrives without consulting Tsomo and starts living with her, eventually forming a marital relationship. The description of Tsomo's attempt to reject Lhatu's proposal, only to have him ignore her wishes and choose to remain with her, highlights the lack of agency women often face in making life decisions. This scenario depicts a societal dynamic where women's voices and choices are disregarded. It reflects the limitations imposed by societal expectations and gender roles. The novel vividly illustrates how women, consciously or unconsciously, often submit to men. Marriage, as portrayed, often offers women in society a false sense of status and protection. Choden emphasizes that women tend to receive similar treatment whether they are married or not, and marriage does not automatically grant them elevated status. Any respect and dignity a woman receives from her spouse is attributed solely to him, and women are often misled into believing falsehoods about their standing within the marital relationship. This underscores the pervasive and unjust power dynamics present in the portrayal of women's roles in the narrative. Tsomo and Lhatu develop a relationship reminiscent of a

master and servant. Tsomo attends to all of Lhatu's needs while he remains mostly secluded, exchanging only minimal words with her. He spends extended periods outside throughout the day, returning only in the evenings. It can be observed that Tsomo is being utilized solely to fulfill Lhatu's needs. Despite Tsomo being the primary earner, she finds herself emotionally dependent on Lhatu, who spends his days doing very little and often complains about his perceived dignity. As their financial situation worsens, Tsomo decides to take up work as a coolie and discusses it with Lhatu. However, burdened by the traditional expectation that husbands should provide for their wives, he becomes angry at the suggestion. Men like Lhatu, despite not actively assuming their responsibilities, resist the idea of their wives working outside the home and are only comfortable if their wives confine their work to the domestic sphere. Expressions like 'Shooyud' by Lhatu towards Tsomo indicate a condescending tone, typically used to threaten a child or subordinate or even shoo away a dog. This highlights Lhatu's expectation of his wife to be humble and obedient to him. Lhatu's frequent absence from the house, ostensibly for work, is revealed as a pretense as he engages in gambling while Tsomo is the primary earner. The unequal treatment is evident as Tsomo is not regarded as an equal partner but a servant in their relationship. Despite Lhatu gambling away everything Tsomo earned or crafted, he audaciously asserts that Tsomo, being a woman without merit, is merely reaping the rewards of his supposedly good karma. In her relationship with her spouse, a wife is often perceived as an extension of him. She is expected to support and assist him. Social recognition of her is restricted to her role as his spouse, overshadowing her true identity. A woman does not inherently have her independent standing. Before marriage, she assumes her father's social standing, and after marriage, she adopts her husband's rank. This portrayal underscores the societal expectations and limitations placed on women, defining their worth primarily through their marital roles rather than recognizing their individual identities. Lhatu wields complete authority over Tsomo, exercising control and dominance. Their relationship lacks emotional connection, and Tsomo finds herself resenting her destiny. When Tsomo discovers her husband's extramarital affair, she chooses not to confront him directly. Instead, she opts to address the other women involved in the situation. Despite all Tsomo did for Lhatu, he falls for a younger woman. This leaves Tsomo feeling worthless. Even though she recognizes that Lhatu is a burden and his departure means freedom, the sense of being deemed valueless weighs on her the most. Having experienced repeated exploitation by the men in her life, Tsomo ultimately opts for a life of celibacy. In time, Tsomo, in the story, transcends her assigned roles and the confined spaces within marriages, evolving into a self-aware and independent individual. This suggests a transformation in her personal growth and a departure from the traditional societal expectations that initially constrained them. The narrative portrays a journey towards individual empowerment and liberation from societal norms. In the end, it is within religion that she discovers solace. Tsomo's ultimate choice to seek refuge in religion by becoming a nun reflects the societal triumph in breaking such a woman. It encapsulates the prevailing status of women in Bhutanese society during that era, illustrating the challenges and limitations they faced, often leading them to find solace and identity within religious roles. As the story progresses,

Tsomo confronts profound inner turmoil and a stark confrontation with life's harsh realities. Her transgressions lead to realizing the self-centeredness and emptiness inherent in relationships. In the final chapter of the novel, self-discovery becomes a prominent theme. The female protagonists undergo extensive introspection, ultimately culminating in their pivotal life decisions.

Conclusion

By narrating Tsomo's story, an innocent and modest woman persecuted solely for being a woman, Kunzang Choden aims to bring attention to women's challenges in a male-dominated culture. Kunzang closely examines the underlying structure of societal evaluations based on gender and conducts a critical analysis of the social structures created by a patriarchal society to oppress women. The narrative effectively portrays the development of Tsomo's character, shedding light on her discovery of the world and the shaping of her early conceptions of gender, influenced by cultural and familial ideals. Women like Tsomo internalize societal expectations and norms regarding gender roles. This process leads her to accept or internalize certain beliefs about the roles and perceived inferiority or superiority associated with her gender. Her cultural and societal factors often influence these perceptions. Choden explores and critiques these dynamics, shedding light on the impact of gender expectations on individuals' self-perception and societal roles. The protagonist, Tsomo, is portrayed as a single woman ensnared in a web of her desires, societal injustice, and exploitation by men, emphasizing the struggles faced by women within this context. Choden consistently stresses the point that, regardless of the circumstances, women are the ultimate victims and tend to be exploited by men. This recurring theme underscores the challenges and vulnerabilities faced by women in the narrative. In Choden's *The Circle of Karma*, women are often depicted as meek and submissive, hesitant to raise their voices against injustice. Even when Tsomo attempts to resist her first husband, Wangchen, she is met with violence and ultimately compelled to flee. This reflects a pattern of women facing consequences for challenging societal norms, reinforcing the notion of women being subdued and often silenced in the face of oppression. Through the character of Tsomo, Choden unveils the harsh reality of widespread violence and the oppression of women within the societal framework of marriage. While the institution of marriage is ostensibly aimed at regulating sexual relationships, Choden portrays that its primary function appears to be the exploitation of women. The novel exposes the ruthless exploitation of women, both within and outside the confines of marriage. Tsomo becomes a victim of exploitation under the guise of marriage. Throughout the narrative, the men that Tsomo encounters adhere to conventional, patriarchal behaviour. The women in the story find themselves helpless and submissive to the men. Despite being betrayed and mistreated, Tsomo enters into relationships because, as a woman, she fears losing the protection that men offer. This highlights the pervasive influence of patriarchal norms and the challenges women face in asserting their independence. Choden has adeptly confronted established gender norms by creating Tsomo, an individual determined not to allow relationships to dictate her identity as a woman. The narrative illustrates Tsomo's internal conflict as

she endeavours to shape her sense of self while grappling with societal expectations regarding women.

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